

Assessment of Peer Influence on Predisposition to Examination Misconduct among Tertiary Institution Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The Study aimed at examining Assessment of Peer Influence on Predisposition to examination misconduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State, Nigeria. Research questions were raised and corresponding hypotheses tested at .05 level of significance. The research design adopted for this study was an ex-post facto research design and the population of this study comprised 35,500 (21,589 Males and 13,911 Females) final-year students in all tertiary institutions in Cross River State, during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample of this study consists of 2,439 (1,079 Males and 1,360 Females) final year students which represents 7% of the total population selected from five tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The instrument used for data collection was "Assessment of Peer Influence on Predisposition to Examination Misconduct Questionnaire (APIPEMQ). Cronbach Alpha reliability test was used to test scores from the questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered once to the respondents after which the coefficient of internal consistency was estimated and the reliability index was 82. Accordingly, which shows that the instrument was reliable for data collection. descriptive statistics was employed to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at .05 level of significance. Findings revealed that Peer assessment does significantly influence students' examination misconduct. It concludes that stake holders in the academic environment are expected to encourage the students to shun all manners of misconduct, amongst others. The researchers recommended among others that, the school management should as a matter of urgency restrict negative peer associations in schools by enacting laws to prevent students from engaging in any form of examination misconduct.

Keywords: Peer association, Predisposition, Examination misconduct, Tertiary institution

Introduction

Education at any level is geared towards an instructional system that deals with teaching, learning and evaluation in a defined environment. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) defined tertiary education as post-secondary education that is offered in universities, polytechnics and colleges of technology. Education is important in the development and improvement of skills. It helps in improving the living standard and condition of the people. According to Morrison et al in Onah, Eteng & Adie (2021) education is the process through which the ideals and worthwhile values of society are systematically passed on from the generation to another to ensure socio-cultural transformation and advancement of man and his environment. That is education makes one a responsible and respectful citizen. Through education, people are enabled to develop their knowledge and skills, adopt new behaviour and be able to survive in the society. The quality of examination refers to the systematic monitoring and evaluation of the various aspects of the programme to maximize the possibility of achieving programme goals. The quality of these goals is measured through tests and examinations Asim (2017). For examinations to be valid, reliable and useable as a potent instrument for judgment of knowledge, every student must be devoid of all forms of malpractices (Haruna,

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et. al., 2023). This is to ensure that whatever grades or certificates a learner is given is a true reflection of the attributes possessed by such a student.

Examination remains the best tool for objective assessment and evaluation of what learners have acquired after a period of schooling. Thus, any compromising action or inaction poses a great danger to the validity, reliability and authenticity of examination results and certificates. Unfortunately, the process of assessment in schools in Nigeria is being marred by the phenomenon of examination misconduct that has become endemic in the educational system. Examination misconduct according to Onyibe *et al.* (2015) manifests in different forms, such as, ‘blocking’, ‘cooperation’, ‘sorting’, ‘cheating’, ‘sexual gratification’ and others. Some other schemes employed by the learners are; impersonation, exchange of answer scripts, fabrication of results, plagiarizing, misrepresentation of identity, tampering with works of others, and unethical use of academic resources. Evidences abound of increasing involvement in examination misconduct behaviour by students. For instance, in 2019, the Federal Ministry of Education blacklisted 316 secondary schools across the nation for their involvement in examination misconduct (Adedigba, 2019). Also, in the May / June 2021 West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (WASSCE) in Nigeria, it was reported that out of 1,590,173 candidates, 180, 205 candidate’s results were withheld over examination misconduct (Ogwo, 2022). Examination misconduct has been seen as a serious problem facing the educational system in contemporary.

Examination misconduct is anything done by examination candidates that is likely to render the assessment in education useless. Onyibe *et al.* (2015), posited that examination misconduct as all aspect of dishonesty or illegal deeds or actions that are carried out by students either personally or using other people like security officers, invigilators, parents, teachers either earlier, during or at the end of examination so as to obtain unmerited grade or marks. Animasahum and Ogunniran (2014) described it as an act that contravenes the rules and regulations of a particular period of time. This implies that it is any activity or activities carried out by students during an examination such that are likely to change the result of the assessment. There are various factors that can be said to be responsible for examination malpractice in our schools. According to Afuge (2015) general moral decadence and the high premium placed on achievement and certificates by Nigerians have in recent times spawned examination fraud. The general overdependence on educational certification as a measure of one’s knowledge and competence has led to a mad rush by most people for educational certificates. In a bid to acquire such certificates, many have resorted to unethical practices just to acquire the certificates at all costs. According to Salvador (2020), a peer is a person who is equal to another in ability, qualification, age, background and social status. That is to say, a peer is a person who belongs to the same age group or social group. Oloshola (2016), see peer group as important socialization agent. For them participating in peer group activities are a primary stage of development and adolescent identities are often closely associated with that of their peers Furo (2015), indicate that peer pressure refers to the way people of the same social group act or believe to influence one another often in negative ways. Peer group pressure is something everybody has to deal with at some time in life because how successfully one handles peer pressure depends so greatly on the individual’s self-concept and position in the world (Ogunbiade and Ajayi, 2018). Irouje (2015) and Okories (2018) emphasized that peer pressure has a much more impact on adolescents’ behaviour than any other factor. They further observed that adolescent interaction with their peers is direct and much more powerful than the influence of counselors, teachers and other authority figures. The teenagers spend much of their working hours with peers than with family members. Okories (2018), Irouje (2015) noted that peer pressure has both negative and positive impacts on the attitude of adolescents towards examination malpractice. The growing menace of examination malpractice in our schools is becoming a worrisome and disturbing phenomenon. The author correctly noted that peer pressure has environmental factors capable of influencing student attitudes towards examination malpractice positively or negatively. Okories (2018) noted that research such as peer cluster theory has shown that peer pressure has a much greater impact on adolescent behaviour than any other factor. The author added that peer influence can increase students’ tendency to involvement in examination misconduct.

Aquibiade and Ajayi (2018), investigated test anxiety and peer influence on secondary school students’ involvement in examination malpractices. The study was carried out in Lagos metropolis. The population for the study consists of secondary school students in education district II in Lagos State. The study adopted ex-post-facto design and made use of a sample of 250 students randomly selected from five senior secondary school in the area of the study. Research instrument titled “Test anxiety and peer influence on secondary school students’ involvement in Examination Malpractices Questionnaire (EMQ)” was used for data collection. Three hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. Data collected were analyzed using one and two-way analysis of variance statistics. The study’s finding revealed that high test anxiety and high peer influence resulted in high involvement in examination malpractices among secondary school students. It was also found that test anxiety and peer influence jointly determine involvement in examination malpractice among the student. It was recommended that student

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should invest sufficient time to their studies and engage in group discussion for effective learning and multiple streams of ideas. Student should avoid keeping bad and unprofitable association so that they will not be laved into examination malpractices. They should associate with people of integrity who will positively influence their value systems and behaviors. This study employed an ex-post-facto to design as opposed to the cross-sectional design employed in the present study.

Also, Okorodudu (2015) conducted a study on peer pressure and socio-economic status as influence on students' attitude to examination malpractice in Nigeria. The questionnaire was used to elicit the right responses on peer pressures and students' attitude toward examination malpractice, using simple regression statistics on the data collected from a sample of 1000 junior secondary two students. The outcome of the study revealed a strong relationship between peer pressure and students' attitude examination behavior. Anierobi *et al.* (2018) studied peer influence and secondary school students' attitude towards examination malpractice in Anambra State. Two research questions and two hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The correlation survey design was adopted for the study. The participants were selected through simple random sampling. A total of 1300 SS2 students from the population of 8,978 SS2 students in the 174 co-educational public secondary schools in Anambra State made up the sample for the study. Three sets of questionnaires titled "Self-Esteem Scale (SES)", "Peer Influence Scale (PIS)" and "Attitude towards Examination Malpractice Scale (ATEMS)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts and the reliability of the ATEMS and PIS were ascertained using Cronbach alpha and they yielded Cronbach alpha coefficients of 0.85 and 0.76 respectively while the SES yielded 0.74 in the Nigerian secondary school setting. Data were analyzed and hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings showed that peer influence has a negative correlation with students' attitudes towards examination malpractice. Self-esteem has a positive correlation with students' attitude toward examination malpractice. Based on the findings it was concluded that students' have a negative attitude towards examination malpractice based on peer influence. It was recommended among others that students should be encouraged to have a positive sense of worth about themselves and also be enlightened on the strategies of avoiding and or coping with negative peer influence to shun examination malpractice.

Examination misconduct has become one among the cankerworms which has eaten so deep into the fabric of examinations in Nigeria (Ogwo 2022). In tertiary institutions in Cross Rivers State, different forms of examination misconduct persist, which include cheating in examination, stealing of examination papers, impersonation, disturbances during examinations, giraffing, obstruction of supervisors, forgery of results, bribery, substitution for answer sheets, use of coded sign languages, submission of fake passport photograph, improper completion of entry forms among others. students' behaviours during examination in tertiary institutions in Cross Rivers State tend to be so worrisome, showing that they have difficulty in conforming to established norms of behavior (Ekott and Ijeoma 2018). For instance, in 2021/2022 academic session, the researcher had a personal encounter with some final year students who were caught with parts of text books and browsing their phones in the examination hall. When the invigilator confronted them, the culprit started harassing the invigilator. Then the researcher began to wonder why such behaviour could prevail among students in tertiary institution. Could it be as a result of peer's association, family structure, social media, parental encouragement, parental educational level, gender or religious background or any other things?

Many students have lost their morals and confidence in their intellectual ability due to the fact that their mindset is that of involving in examination misconduct for success (Ekott and Ijeoma 2018). Though the Federal Government on its part has promulgated decrees, enacted laws, organized workshops and seminars and some authors have also raised alarms on this menace, examination fraud still persists (Onah Et al 2021). Few studies might have been conducted on this topic but probably not in Cross River State; and some variables of the school used in this work seem to be untouched. It was based on these observable problems and the existing gap that the researcher was interested to conduct a study aimed at examining the influence of social variables on students' predisposition to examination misconduct tendencies in tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to assess peer influence on predisposition to examination miss conduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study intends to:

To access the extent of peer influence on predisposition to examination misconduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

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There is no significant difference between mean response scores of Peer influence on predisposition to examination misconduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State, Nigeria

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is ex-post facto design and the population of this study comprised 35,500 (21,589 Males and 13,911 Females) final year students in all the tertiary institution in Cross River State. The sample of this study consist of 2,439 (1,079 Males and 1,360 Females) respondents which represents 7% of the total population selected from five tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The researcher made instruments, “Peer Association and Students Predisposition to Examination Misconduct Questionnaire (PASPEMQ)” were used for data collected. The face validity of the instruments was carried out by two experts. The instruments were modified after due scrutiny from the experts for face validity. The reliability co-efficient of the Peer Association and Students Predisposition to Examination Misconduct Questionnaire were ascertained using the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Co-efficient. The instrument was administered through the permission of the lecturers to the students in the lecture halls by the researcher with the help of trained research assistants. A letter of introduction from the Department was presented to authorities in the various tertiary institutions to seek permission to conduct the study. The letter contains information about the researcher and the aim of the visit for proper understanding and maximum cooperation before questionnaires are given to respondents. Caution was taken to explain the instructions on how to complete the items on the questionnaires. The instrument was retrieved immediately after completion to prevent attrition, but 5 items were missing in the process, hence, the questionnaire instrument were reduced to 2,434. In analyzing the data, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were employed to answer the research questions and the One-way analysis of variance ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

Result

Hypothesis 1

To test this hypothesis, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied with peer association as factor and examination misconduct as the dependent variable. The F-ratio test was used to test for the significance of the main influence, while Fishers’ least significant Difference (LSD) test was used as post hoc test. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 3: One-Way ANOVA of the Influence of Peer Assessment on Examination Misconduct

Sources of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-vale	p-value
Between Groups	3149.026	2	1574.513	85.379	.000
Within Groups	44831.021	2431	18.441		
Total	47980.046	2433			

*p<.05

Source: Field Data (2023)

The results in Table 4.3 show that the P-value (.000) associated with the computed F-value (85.374) is less than .05. As such, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that Peer association does significantly influence students to examination misconduct tendencies in tertiary institutions. To locate the pair of group mean values that accounted for the observed significant results, Fishers Least Significant Difference (LSD) was applied. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 4: LSD pairwise, Comparison of Peer Association on Examination Misconduct

Peer association	Examination misconduct	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p-values	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High	Moderate	.05758	.23286	.805	-.3990	.5142
	Low	2.32633*	.21802	.000	1.8988	2.7538
Moderate	High	-.05758	.23286	.805	-.5142	.3990
	Low	2.26875*	.20392	.000	1.8689	2.6686
Low	High	-2.32633*	.21802	.000	-2.7538	-1.8988

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Moderate	-2.26875*	.20392	.000	-2.6686	-1.8689
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*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level. Source: Field Data (2023)

The results in Table 3 show that the p-values for the categories of high and low (.000), moderate and low, (.000), low and high (.000) and low and moderate (.000) associated with the computed mean differences (MD) ($2.32633 \leq MD \leq 2.26875$, $MD \leq -2.32633$ and $MD \leq -2.26875$) are less than .05. This means that the pair of high and low, moderate and low, low and high and low and moderate paired comparisons are significant.

Discussion of Findings

Peer influence was measured using the same number of items and response options. Therefore, their descriptive statistics can be validly compared. From the Table, by peer association, the means score obtained by high ($\bar{x} = 16.3377$) is higher while those of low ($\bar{x} 14.0114$) had the least. to examination misconduct in tertiary institutions. It has been established that the level of peer association is a strong factor to students' attitude towards examination misconduct. Most adolescents are highly influenced by their peers, if the adolescents excerpt negative influence, it is bound to affect the overall life style of the students. The finding is in line with the study of Aguibiade and Ajayi (2018) which reveal that peer association positively influence the academic performance and cheating tendency of in-school adolescents. The gap in this study was that only two research questions and hypotheses were used with a standardized instrument. The present study has bridged the lapses in the study by answering one research questions and testing one (1) corresponding null hypotheses. In the same vein, Okorodudu (2015) study revealed a strong relationship between peer pressure and students' attitude examination behaviour. In accordance with the present study, Anierobi, *et al.* (2018) findings which showed that peer influence has a negative correlation with students' attitudes towards examination malpractice. Self-esteem has a positive correlation with students' attitude toward examination malpractice.

Conclusion

The issue of examination misconduct has been in the education sector for too long. It should be confronted from all channels as a menace that has almost completely destroyed the education sector. University education is meant to the learning process for human capital development and where that is not efficiently achieved due to examination misconduct, the products of such a learning process will not be efficient in their various specialized areas. Some Universities are very strict on the issues of examination misconduct but others are weak. Consequently, this is a weak up call for the University Vice Chancellors, Deans of faculties, Head of Departments, Lecturers and all those who can make a difference to be seriously involved in fight against examination misconduct by considering the future impact of this menace on graduate students. Stake holders in the academic environment are expected to encouraging the students to shun all manners of misconduct, the government, parents, churches etc. may need to play major complementary role. Having established the significance of social variables on examination misconduct behavior, it is worth the while to conclude this study by stating that examination misconduct seems to loom larger in recent times and since high values have been attached to academic success, higher price has also been attached examination misconduct which only the high can buy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School management should as a matter of urgency restrict negative peer associations in schools by enacting laws to prevent students from engaging in any form of examination misconduct.
2. The school management should offer students with effective orientation exercises of ethical behaviours with emphasis on examination misconduct.
3. Parents at home should endeavor to teach good morals to their children thus, parents should encourage their children to develop an attitude of diligence and not believe that unethical conduct such as bribing a lecturer (gratifications) could money solve all problems.
4. The school counsellor should counsel students on proper study habits for academic excellence in examination. Government in collaboration with non-governmental organization (NGOs) should create an orientation campaign for all stakeholders in the academic environment on the dangers of over-reliance on certification. One of the major dangers in our educational system is over emphasis on certificates. This has made all students dwell strongly on using any possible means of passing the examination.

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